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Donat CK, Gaber K, Meixensberger J, Brust P, Pinborg LH, Hansen HH, Mikkelsen JD

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1 **Changes in binding of [¹²³I]CLINDE, a high-affinity**
2 **translocator protein 18 kDa (TSPO) selective radioligand in**
3 **a rat model of traumatic brain injury**

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6 Cornelius K. Donat^{1*}, Khaled Gaber², Jürgen Meixensberger², Peter
7 Brust³, Lars H. Pinborg¹, Henrik H. Hansen¹ and Jens D. Mikkelsen¹

¹Neurobiology Research Unit, Copenhagen University Hospital, Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen, Denmark

²Department of Neurosurgery, University of Leipzig, Germany

³Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf, Institute of Radiopharmaceutical Cancer Research, Research Site Leipzig, Dept. of Neuroradiopharmaceuticals, Permoserstrasse 15, 04318 Leipzig, Germany

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9 neuroinflammation

10 * Correspondence:
11 Jens D. Mikkelsen, Neurobiology Research Unit, Copenhagen University Hospital,
12 Rigshospitalet, Blegdamsvej 9, DK-2100, Copenhagen, Denmark
13 Tel: +45 3545 6701; Fax: +45 3545 6713 E-mail: jens.mikkelsen@nru.dk

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1 **Abstract**

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3 After traumatic brain injury (TBI), secondary injuries develop, including neuro-inflammatory
4 processes that contribute to long-lasting impairments. These secondary injuries represent
5 potential targets for treatment and diagnostics. The translocator protein 18 kDa (TSPO) is
6 expressed in activated microglia cells and upregulated in response to brain injury and therefore
7 a potential biomarker of the neuro-inflammatory processes. Second-generation radioligands
8 of TSPO, such as [¹²³I]CLINDE, have a higher signal-to-noise ratio as the prototype ligand
9 PK11195. [¹²³I]CLINDE has been employed in human studies using Single-photon emission
10 computed tomography to image the neuro-inflammatory response after stroke. In this study,
11 we used the same tracer in a rat model of TBI to determine changes in TSPO expression.

12 Adult Sprague-Dawley rats were subjected to moderate Controlled-Cortical-Impact injury at
13 the M1 motor cortex, and sacrificed at 6h, 24h, 72h, and 28 days post-surgery. TSPO
14 expression was assessed in brain sections employing [¹²³I]CLINDE *in vitro* autoradiography.

15 From 24 h to 28 days post-surgery, injured animals exhibited a marked and time-dependent
16 increase of CLINDE binding in the ipsilateral motor, somatosensory and parietal cortex, as well
17 as in the hippocampus and thalamus. Interestingly, binding was also significantly elevated in
18 the contralateral M1 motor cortex following TBI. Craniotomy without TBI caused a less marked
19 increase in [¹²³I]CLINDE binding, restricted to the ipsilateral hemisphere. Radioligand binding
20 was consistent with an increase in TSPO mRNA expression and CD11b immunoreactivity at
21 the contusion site.

22 This study demonstrates the applicability of [¹²³I]CLINDE for detailed regional and
23 quantitative assessment of glial activity in experimental models of TBI.

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1 **Introduction**

2 Traumatic brain injury (TBI) is a disease with many different symptoms and transient to life-
3 long cognitive and sensorimotor disabilities. The complex and intertwined mechanisms
4 responsible for these disabilities can be roughly separated in primary and secondary injuries.
5 The primary injury is the initial biomechanical trauma (Stemper and Pintar 2014), a process
6 that causes neuronal, axonal and vascular damage induced by the kinetic energy. However,
7 this primary trauma triggers a cascade of secondary processes that result in excitotoxicity,
8 necrosis, apoptosis, autophagy and free radical formation (Blennow et al. 2012). Due to this
9 cascade of events, TBI is considered to be a chronic disease (Masel and DeWitt 2010).
10 Furthermore this implicates that the pathological processes take place in the injured brain at
11 different times after the injury, where some are beneficial to recovery and others are triggered
12 by and aggravating the initial damage.

13 One of the key features of TBI is the robust inflammatory response, characterized by release
14 of cytokines and chemokines (Woodcock and Morganti-Kossmann 2013), activation of glia
15 cells in the brain and invasion of peripheral immune cells, e.g. leukocytes and macrophages
16 due to leakiness of the blood-brain-barrier (Lozano et al. 2015). The inflammatory response in
17 TBI represents both beneficial/restorative and detrimental/degenerative mechanisms in the
18 restorative process (Schwarzmaier and Plesnila 2014). Pro-inflammatory stimuli trigger
19 morphological and functional changes of microglia, the principal immune cells of the brain,
20 termed “microglia activation”. An important result of microglia activation is the change of the
21 translocator protein 18 kDa (TSPO), located at the contact sites between the outer and inner
22 mitochondrial membrane (Jaremko et al. 2014). This protein is expressed at low levels in the
23 healthy brain, but markedly upregulated in response to injury (Papadopoulos and Lecanu
24 2009) and neuroinflammation (Chen and Guilarte 2008). This upregulation is associated with
25 microglia activation, however not restricted to these cells alone. TSPO upregulation was also
26 reported on astrocytes (Kuhlmann and Guilarte 2000; Maeda et al. 2007) co-localized with
27 selective radioligand binding (Yu et al. 2010). Irrespectively of the triggering event and
28 underlying cellular source of the TSPO changes, its upregulation is regarded as an important

1 biomarker of neuroinflammation (Liu et al. 2014) and brain injury (Papadopoulos and Lecanu
2 2009) . Notably, imaging changes in TSPO binding with selective radiotracers in patients offers
3 a unique opportunity to study inflammatory processes *in vivo*. For this purpose, a number of
4 radiolabelled small molecules with superior affinity and selectivity, compared to the prototypical
5 TSPO ligand PK11195, have been developed (Trapani et al. 2013). Specifically, 6-chloro-2-
6 (4'-(123)I-iodophenyl)-3-(N,N-diethyl)-imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine-3-acetamide (CLINDE) is such a
7 second-generation ligand, characterized by high affinity, brain uptake and signal to noise ratio
8 (Arlicot et al. 2008; Mattner et al. 2008). In preclinical settings, CLINDE was found to be
9 selective for TSPO, characterized by lack of specific binding in TSPO knock-out mice (Banati
10 et al. 2014) and robust upregulation of TSPO binding was previously demonstrated in animal
11 models of e.g. excitotoxicity, focal ischemia and experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis
12 (Mattner et al. 2005; Arlicot et al. 2008; Arlicot et al. 2010; Mattner et al. 2011; Arlicot et al.
13 2014). Furthermore, our research group recently applied CLINDE to image regulation of TSPO
14 in patients with cerebral stroke or glioblastoma, where it was found to predict infarct size and
15 tumour progression, respectively (Feng et al. 2014; Jensen et al. 2015a). More importantly,
16 CLINDE was able to show the effect of immunotherapy in a patient suffering from anti-NMDA
17 receptor encephalitis (Jensen et al. 2015b). However, as most of the second-generation TSPO
18 ligands (Owen et al. 2010), CLINDE binding in humans is affected by the rs6971 single-
19 nucleotide polymorphism, resulting in high, mixed and low-affinity binders (Feng et al. 2014).
20 In animal models of TBI, CLINDE might serve as a biomarker to monitor and quantify
21 therapeutic effects. In order to study the time- and region-dependent changes of TSPO after
22 TBI, we assessed TSPO binding by employing *in vitro* [¹²³I]CLINDE autoradiography.

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1 **Materials and methods**

2 The experimental protocols were approved by the local ethic committee. All animal
3 experiments were authorized by the local governmental authorities (license number TVV
4 22/09).

5

6 Controlled Cortical Impact model of Traumatic Brain Injury

7 For the experiments, a total of 64 male, adult (55-70 days, weight: 291 ± 31 g) Sprague-Dawley
8 rats (Janvier, France) were used with post-surgery survival time-points of 6, 24, 72 hours and
9 28 days. Each time point consisted of 16 rats that were randomly assigned to receive either
10 TBI (n=5), craniotomy (n=3) or sham operation (n=5). Additional three rats per group received
11 no anaesthesia or surgery and served as naive controls.

12 Prior to the experiments, animals were kept in cages (4-6 in each) under controlled conditions
13 of temperature and humidity and were subjected to a 12/12 hours dark/light-cycle. After
14 surgery, animals were housed in individual cages with nutrition and water ad libitum.

15 Surgical procedures and the injury model were previously described in detail (Donat et al.
16 2007; Donat et al. 2008). Rats were intramuscularly anaesthetized with fentanyl (0.005 mg/kg,
17 Janssen, Germany), midazolam (2 mg/kg, Ratiopharm, Germany) and medetomidine (0.15
18 mg/kg, Pfizer, Germany). The animals received perioperative analgesia with metamizole (100
19 mg/kg, Ratiopharm, Germany).

20 Body temperature was maintained at 37°C during surgery through a thermistor rectal probe
21 feedback-controlled heating pad (FHC Inc., USA). Subsequently, the animals were placed in
22 a stereotaxic frame, the hair was removed and the scalp disinfected with povidoneiodine. A
23 midline incision exposed the skull (Sham, Craniotomy and TBI group).

24 Animals (craniotomy and TBI group) were subjected to a unilateral 6 mm circular craniotomy
25 with an electrical dental drill over the M1 motor cortex (3.5 mm posterior, +4.0 mm lateral to
26 bregma) of the left hemisphere, with intact dura. The bone flap was stored in sterile saline until
27 reimplantation.

1 For TBI, a unilateral focal injury (TBI group, Controlled-Cortical-Impact, CCI) to the left
2 hemisphere was induced with a 5-mm-diameter rounded metal impactor, electromagnetically
3 driven by a CCI device (Custom Design and Fabrication, Virginia Commonwealth University,
4 USA). The exposed dura was hit by the impactor for 100 ms at a velocity of 4 m/s and a depth
5 of 2 mm, resulting in a moderate injury (Yu et al. 2009). For craniotomy, the brain was exposed
6 to serve as a control for the surgery procedure. Immediately after this procedure, the bone flap
7 was replaced and fixed with a non-toxic light-curing embedding resin (TechnoVit® 7200,
8 Heraeus Kulzer, Germany). The incision was sutured (in case of the 6 hour group, animals
9 were stapled) and anaesthesia antagonized with a subcutaneous injection of a mixture of
10 naloxone (0.12 mg/kg, Ratiopharm, Germany), flumazenil (0.2 mg/kg, Roche, Germany) and
11 atipamezole (0.75 mg/kg, Pfizer, Germany). The rats were returned to individual cages and
12 received postoperative analgesia with metamizole, once injected postoperatively (100 mg/kg
13 metamizole i.m) and later added to the drinking water. At designated times after CCI, rats were
14 lightly anaesthetized with the same mixture as described above and the animals subsequently
15 decapitated. After decapitation, the brain was quickly removed and immediately frozen in -
16 40°C 2-methylbutane for at least 30 s and stored at -80°C C for further processing.

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18 Tissue preparation

19 Coronal whole-brain sections (12 µm) were cut with a cryostat microtome (MICROM HM 560,
20 Walldorf, Germany), mounted onto untreated glass slides [25x45 mm (3 sections); Carl Roth,
21 Germany], briefly dried at room temperature and stored at -28°C until further processing.

22

23 In vitro autoradiography of [¹²³I]CLINDE

24 [¹²³I]CLINDE was supplied by MAP Medical Technologies Oy (Tikkakoski, Finland), prepared
25 according to GMP standards for clinical use with a maximum specific activity (SA) of 8800
26 TBq/mmol.

1 Autoradiography was performed similar to previously published methods with [¹²⁵I]CLINDE
2 (Mattner et al. 2011). To achieve a concentration of three nMol/L, the specific activity was
3 lowered by adding unlabelled CLINDE (supplied by Dr. N. Arlicot) to the assay buffer.
4 All sections were thawed for 15 minutes at room temperature (RT) and 20 min pre-incubated
5 in assay buffer (50 mM TRIS-HCl, pH 7.4/RT). Afterwards, the sections were incubated under
6 gentle agitation for 60 minutes at RT with assay buffer containing the radioligand. Non-specific
7 binding was determined on adjacent sections of the same animal with the radioligand and 10
8 μM PK11195 (Biotrend, Switzerland). Subsequently, slides were washed for 2x2 min in
9 washing buffer (50 mM TRIS-HCl, pH 7.4/4°C) and 30 sec in ice-cold ultra-pure water. All
10 slides were then air-stream dried for 20 minutes and exposed to BAS-SR2540 imaging plates
11 (Fuji Film, Tokyo, Japan) together with ¹⁴C- standards (0146N, American Radiolabelled
12 Chemicals, USA) for 20 minutes.

13

14 Autoradiography data analysis

15 For analysis of [¹²³I]CLINDE binding, imaging plates were scanned using a Bioimager (BAS
16 2500, Fuji), converted to TIF-files using the manufacturer's software and analysed in
17 QuantityOne (BioRad, Waltham, USA). Regions of interest (ROIs) were drawn over the primary
18 motor cortex, hippocampus, thalamus, parietal association and barrel field of the primary
19 somatosensory cortex, confirmed by Nissl and Gallays staining (Figure 1/2 B) on adjacent
20 sections of naïve animals (Figure 1/2 C). All ROIs were determined in each single animal
21 (within-subject design) in triplicate (three sections per animal). Mean values of optical density
22 per mm² were converted to radioactive concentration using a linear regression derived from
23 the ¹⁴C-radioactive standards. A global background was subtracted and the values were
24 normalized to the mean values of the corresponding brain regions of the naïve group. Final
25 values are expressed as percentage of mean naïve.

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1 Immunohistochemistry

2 Coronal sections were fixed for 20 min in 4% paraformaldehyde solution (in phosphate
3 buffered saline, PBS) at 4 °C. Slides were washed afterwards 3x10 min in PBS and were dried
4 at RT.

5 Sections were quenched with hydrogen peroxide (0.6%) and MeOH (10%) in PBS. Slides were
6 washed again (3x5 min) in 1x PBS and afterwards incubated in blocking solution (5% normal
7 goat serum, 2% BSA, 0.2% Triton X-100 in PBS) to block endogenous peroxidase and non-
8 specific binding, respectively. Sections were then incubated overnight at 4 °C in a humidified
9 chamber with the primary mouse monoclonal antibody OX-42 (1:500; AbD Serotec, Puchheim,
10 Germany), recognising the complement type 3 receptor present on cells of microglial lineage,
11 as well as granulocytes and dendritic cells (Robinson et al. 1986). Afterwards, the sections
12 were rinsed 3x10 min in PBS and the incubated 90 min in secondary polyclonal anti-mouse
13 biotinylated (1:1000 with 2% BSA and 0.2% TX in PBS, Jackson ImmunoResearch, West
14 Grove, USA). Slides were washed again 3x10 min in PBS before incubation for 1 h with 0.4%
15 avidin–biotin–peroxidase complex solution (Vectastain ABC kit, Vector Laboratories,
16 Burlingame, USA) in PBS with 0.1% TX. After rinsing (3x10 min in PBS), the immunoreaction
17 was developed with diaminobenzidine as chromagen (0.1% DAB and 0.03% H₂O₂ in Tris–HCl,
18 pH 7.6). Slides were dehydrated in an ascending series of ethanol, followed by xylene and
19 mounted in Pertex. Images were digitized with a CCD scanner (HP ScanJet 3800).

20

21 Real Time Quantitative PCR

22 For determination of mRNA levels of TSPO with qPCR, additional 5 animals were subjected
23 to TBI or sham-operation.

24 Total RNA was extracted from sampled frozen tissue blocks (~1mm³, taken from the injured
25 M1 motor cortex), with an RNeasy Mini Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) according to the
26 manufacturer's protocol, and dissolved in RNase-free water. The content of RNA was
27 determined with a Nanodrop ND-2000 spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham,
28 USA). Extracted RNA was reverse transcribed into single-stranded cDNA with the ImPromII™

1 Reverse Transcription System (Promega, Madison, USA) according to the manufacturer's
2 protocol using oligo(dT) 15 primers, 6 mM MgCl₂, and 20 units of RNase inhibitor. Real-time
3 RT-qPCR reactions were performed in a total volume of 20 µl, containing 5 µl sample cDNA,
4 10 µl 2×Brilliant II SYBR® Green qPCR Master Mix (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, USA),
5 15 pmol each of the forward and reverse primer (DNA Technology, Aarhus, Denmark), and
6 combined with distilled water to the final volume. Non-template and non-enzyme controls were
7 also included.

8 The primers used in these experiments were confirmed by gel electrophoresis with the
9 sequence as following. GAPDH (NM_017008.4) Forward: CATCAAGAAGGTGGTGAAGCA,
10 Reverse: CTGTTGAAGTCACAGGAGACA and TSPO (NM_012515) Forward:
11 GCTGCCCGCTTGCTGTATCCT and Reverse CCCTCGCCGACCAGAGTTATCA according
12 to (Lavisse et al. 2012).

13 PCR was performed on a Light Cycler 480 (Roche, Indianapolis, USA) with a 130 sec
14 preincubation at 95 °C followed by 45 cycles of 5 s at 95 °C, 30 s at 60 °C and 1 cycle of 1 s
15 at 50 °C and 5 min at 40 °C. Each primer pair was validated by using serially diluted cDNA
16 from a randomly selected RNA sample to establish a standard curve. Quantification of mRNA
17 expression was performed according to the comparative CT method (Schmittgen and Livak
18 2008). For each sample, the amount of target mRNA was normalized to that of the reference
19 gene GAPDH.

20

21 Statistical processing

22 Differences between groups (autoradiography and RT-qPCR) were tested with an unpaired
23 two-tailed Student's *t*-test, with significance levels of $\alpha=0.05$.

24

25 *Insert Figure 1 about here*

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1 **Results**

2 *In vitro autoradiography of [¹²³I]CLINDE*

3 *In vitro* autoradiography employing the TSPO selective radioligand [¹²³I]CLINDE showed that
4 binding in the brain of sham-operated and drug/surgery naïve animals was very low and nearly
5 uniform at all investigated time points. Higher binding in these control groups was observed in
6 the rhinal fissure, rhinal incisura at the motor cortex level (Figure 1A). Sham and naïve animals
7 showed slightly higher binding in subcortical structures, especially in thalamic and
8 hypothalamic structures, the hippocampal fissure and over the ventricular ependymal in the
9 dorsal part and the posterior portion of the 3rd ventricle as well as in the lateral ventricles (Figure
10 2A).

11 Nonspecific binding, assessed with 10 µM PK11195, was uniform across all investigated
12 groups, indicating high selectivity and signal-to-noise ratio of the radioligand.

13

14 *Time-dependent increase of [¹²³I]CLINDE binding after focal TBI*

15 Binding at the injury site (Interaural 12.20 mm, Bregma 3.20 mm):

16 In TBI-injured animals, a distinct temporal and brain regional upregulation of TSPO binding
17 was observed in the proximity of the injury as demonstrated in representative autoradiographs
18 in Figure 1A and 3A.

19 At 6 hours post injury, no significant changes of [¹²³I]CLINDE binding in the cortex were
20 observed. However, after 24 h, TBI-injured animals exhibited a two-fold increase in radioligand
21 binding compared to craniotomy and sham (P<0.05 and P<0.01, respectively). Craniotomy
22 alone also caused a significantly higher binding as compared to sham (P<0.05) (Fig. 3A).

23 CLINDE binding was maximally elevated at 72 h post-surgery, in TBI animals as well as in
24 craniotomized animals (as compared to the sham-operated group, P < 0.01). However, there
25 was no significant difference in the CLINDE binding level between TBI and craniotomy at this
26 time point.

27 At 28 days post-surgery, CLINDE binding remained approximately two-fold elevated in the TBI-
28 injured and craniotomized animals, as compared to shams (P<0.001), but no differences were
29 found between these two groups.

1 Craniotomized animals showed no changes in CLINDE binding in the contralateral motor
2 cortex. In contrast, all animals subjected to TBI exhibited a moderately increased CLINDE
3 binding in the contralateral motor cortex both at 24 and 72 h post-surgery (Fig. 1A and 3A,
4 $P < 0.05$).

5

6 *Insert Figure 2 about here*

7

8 Binding in other regions (Interaural 5.20 mm, Bregma -3.80 mm):

9 As illustrated in autoradiographs in Figure 2A/3B, both TBI and craniotomized controls animals
10 exhibited a distinct and time-dependent pattern of CLINDE binding in brain regions that were
11 not directly affected by the mechanical injury.

12 At 6 h post-surgery, only minor changes in hippocampus, thalamus, parietal association cortex
13 and barrel field of the primary somatosensory cortex were observed.

14 The parietal and somatosensory cortices showed a moderate but significant increase of
15 [^{123}I]CLINDE binding at 24 h post-surgery in the TBI-injured ($P < 0.01$) and craniotomy ($P < 0.01$)
16 groups compared to sham, but not between each other.

17 The most pronounced increases in [^{123}I]CLINDE binding were found at 72 hours post-surgery.
18 In the parietal cortex, TBI caused a nearly three-fold increase of radioligand binding ($P < 0.001$),
19 similar to the two-fold increase of craniotomized animals ($P < 0.001$) compared to the sham
20 group. This pattern was also observed in the somatosensory cortex in TBI-injured (+239%,
21 $P < 0.001$) and craniotomized animals (+155%, $P < 0.01$). Additionally, the whole hippocampus
22 of rats subjected to TBI showed a small but significantly elevated binding (+36%, $P < 0.01$).

23 In contrast, no significant hippocampal alterations were found in the subacute phase at 28
24 days post-surgery. Both parietal (+77%, $P < 0.001$) and somatosensory (+87%, $P < 0.001$)
25 cortices showed elevated CLINDE binding in animal subjected to TBI and craniotomy (+77%,
26 $P < 0.05$; +80%, $P < 0.01$) after 28 days.

27 In the thalamus (primarily the ventral posteromedial thalamic nucleus), changes were only
28 detected at 28 d post-surgery, and not at any other time-point. The increase in radioligand

1 binding was significantly different from sham-operated ($P < 0.01$) and craniotomized rats
2 ($P < 0.05$). Across all time points, no significant differences were observed in the corresponding
3 structures of the contralateral hemisphere (data not shown).

4

5 *Insert Figure 3 about here.*

6

7 TSPO mRNA levels correspond to increases of [123 I]CLINDE binding in the motor cortex at 72
8 hours post injury.

9 In extracts from the M1 motor cortex of animals subjected to TBI, an eight-fold increase of
10 TSPO mRNA was found at 72 hours post injury when compared to sham ($P < 0.0001$) (Fig 4).

11

12 *Insert Figure 4 about here.*

13 OX-42 immunopositive cells are concentrated in the contusion of the injured M1 motor cortex
14 and match the distribution of [123 I]CLINDE binding at 72 hours post injury.

15 Immunostaining using the OX-42 (CD11b) antibody revealed a high number of OX-42
16 immunopositive cells in the contusion (Figure 5 left image) at 72 h post-surgery. The
17 distribution of OX-42 immunoreactivity overlapped with the strongest increase in radioligand
18 binding (Figure 5 middle and right image).

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20 *Insert Figure 5 about here.*

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1 **Discussion**

2 This study investigated changes in TSPO expression after TBI, employing the selective
3 radioligand [¹²³I]CLINDE. CLINDE is a second-generation TSPO ligand, with a high signal-to-
4 noise ratio, low nanomolar affinity (Mattner et al. 2008) and absence of specific binding in
5 TSPO knockout mice (Banati et al. 2014). The observed brain regional TSPO binding pattern
6 was similar to that reported for other TSPO radioligands (Banati et al. 1997).

7 CLINDE is of clinical relevance, as it has been used recently to image changes of TSPO in
8 patients with cerebral stroke and glioblastoma, respectively (Feng et al. 2014; Jensen et al.
9 2015a; Jensen et al. 2015b). The low expression of TSPO in the healthy brain of man, rodents
10 and nonhuman primates (Collste et al. 2015; Lavisse et al. 2015; Toth et al. 2015) and the
11 robust upregulation in response to brain injury (Liu et al. 2014), allows a qualitative and
12 quantitative assessment of neuroinflammation-associated changes. This study further
13 supports the use of [¹²³I]CLINDE for detecting changes in TSPO binding after brain injury.

14 Glia cells are activated after TBI, leading to reactive astrocytic gliosis (Burda and Sofroniew
15 2014) and microglia activation (Norden et al. 2015) and both processes are implicated in the
16 long-term neuropathology of the disease (reviewed in (Faden et al. 2015). Modulation of the
17 neuro-inflammatory response after TBI is therefore regarded as an important treatment
18 strategy. Because microglia exert both neuroprotective and neurotoxic functions, depending
19 on their activation pattern and phenotype (Benarroch 2013), it must be emphasized that
20 changes in TSPO binding represents a composite measure of both effects.

21 In the present study, a strong increase in [¹²³I]CLINDE binding was found 24 hours post-TBI at
22 the site of the injury, peaking at 72 hours and was still significantly elevated in the subacute
23 phase after 28 days. This temporal profile is similar to that reported in other TBI models
24 (Raghavendra Rao et al. 2000; Yu et al. 2010; Cao et al. 2012). In addition, there is a
25 remarkable match of *in vitro* binding and *in vivo* uptake of [¹⁸F]DPA-714 after transient focal
26 ischemia, especially one month post-injury (Martin et al. 2010), which lends support to the
27 translatability of *in vitro* CLINDE binding assay to *in vivo* imaging.

1 qPCR analysis revealed an increase of TSPO mRNA in a comparable magnitude, which further
2 demonstrates target selectivity of CLINDE and, importantly, also indicates that [¹²³I]CLINDE
3 binding directly reflects corresponding changes in TSPO expression. qPCR allows a sensitive
4 evaluation in very small quantity samples. Selective analysis of activated immune cells, e.g.
5 by CD11b separation, could furthermore be used to determine microglia phenotype dynamics
6 (Kumar et al. 2015). Depending to their phenotype, microglia can act as mediators of
7 progressive tissue regeneration or chronic degeneration, and modulation of these processes
8 provide potential treatment options. In contrast, molecular imaging investigates changes of the
9 targeted protein and offers translatability to the clinics e.g. through non-invasive PET/SEPCT
10 imaging of human subjects.

11 Craniotomy induced a less pronounced increase in CLINDE binding in most of the ipsilateral
12 brain structures, likely caused by perturbations to the dura mater and the surface of the
13 cerebral cortex and therefore subsequently induces inflammatory changes. In agreement with
14 our observation, others have reported that craniotomy induces brain injury, behavioural
15 impairments and a profound inflammatory response (Cole et al. 2011; Lagraoui et al. 2012). It
16 may thus be argued that craniotomy is not an appropriate control in open-skull models of TBI,
17 as it may potentially mask specific effects of TBI *per se* and lead to an underestimation of
18 therapeutic effects. Our findings clearly indicate that TBI promotes a more marked brain
19 damage and consequently larger increase in CLINDE binding. Furthermore, in contrast to TBI,
20 craniotomy had no effect on CLINDE binding in the ipsilateral thalamus 28 days post-injury,
21 hippocampus and in the contralateral cortex.

22 The delayed thalamic TSPO increase at 28 days post-TBI points to a specific vulnerability
23 (reviewed in (Grossman and Inglese 2016), suggesting the thalamus as a target of secondary
24 inflammation. This is frequently observed after TBI in animal models (Raghavendra Rao et al.
25 2000; Grossman et al. 2003; Kelso et al. 2009; Yu et al. 2010; Folkersma et al. 2011b; Cao et
26 al. 2012) and patients (Folkersma et al. 2011a; Ramlackhansingh et al. 2011), where it
27 correlates with persistent white matter damage (Scott et al. 2015). Similar changes are
28 reported after stroke in rats (Myers et al. 1991) and humans (Pappata et al. 2000). This

1 increase in regions distal from the cortical primary injury occurs long after the initial damage
2 and in areas known to project directly to the site of damage, i.e. the ventrolateral thalamic
3 nuclei and in contralateral brain areas indicating that microglial activation could spread along
4 damaged white matter tracts.

5 Similarly, contralateral cortical increases of TSPO radiotracer uptake were reported before (Yu
6 et al. 2010). The underlying mechanisms for the TSPO increase in these regions are not clear,
7 but it is tempting to speculate that activated microglia are also involved in compensatory
8 restoration of neuronal function, which may occur at the contralateral hemisphere. In rodent
9 models of stroke, microglia suppression leads to long-term decreases of neuronal plasticity
10 markers, e.g. brain-derived neurotrophic factor (Madinier et al. 2009) and contralesional
11 pyramidal tract plasticity was found to promote recovery (Liu et al. 2011; Herz et al. 2012). The
12 detection of small, however relevant changes in TSPO binding levels in areas presumed to be
13 associated with neuroregeneration and synaptic plasticity, requires highly sensitive TSPO
14 tracer ligands, and our study therefore suggests that [¹²³I]CLINDE may be useful not only to
15 detect detrimental consequences of CNS injury, but also to reveal possible regeneration
16 potential long after the insult has taken place.

17 Our findings are in line with previous TBI studies where CCI injury in rats caused increased
18 TSPO radioligand binding and mRNA levels at the contusion site (Raghavendra Rao et al.
19 2000; Venneti et al. 2007; Guseva et al. 2008; Kelso et al. 2009). After fluid percussion,
20 [³H]PK11195 binding was increased at day seven post injury in the somatosensory cortex and
21 thalamus, while after 28 days only the thalamus retained the significant increase (Cao et al.
22 2012). Similar increases of TSPO are reported in other models of TBI (Miyazawa et al. 1995;
23 Grossman et al. 2003; Soustiel et al. 2008).

24 *In vivo* [¹¹C]PK11195 and [¹⁸F]DPA-714 -uptake was increased after CCI in rats (Folkersma et
25 al. 2011b) peaking at day 6 and slowly decreasing until 28 days post injury (Wang et al. 2014).
26 Lateral fluid percussion injury increased uptake of [¹⁸F]FE-DAA1106 in the ipsi- and
27 contralateral cortex, striatum and thalamus (Yu et al. 2010), followed by a delayed increase in
28 tracer accumulation in the white matter at 9 weeks post injury, indicating axonal injury.

1 Disruption of the blood-brain-barrier, with an immediate opening in the first hours and a delayed
2 perturbation around three days (Baldwin et al. 1996; Baskaya et al. 1997) should be considered
3 for *in vivo* studies. This could affect the radioligand uptake, as observed after ischemia with
4 increased tracer delivery ratios from day four on, indicating a higher uptake in the injured
5 hemisphere (Martin et al. 2010).

6 The most interesting perspective is to what extent these tracers are useful in human patients
7 of TBI and other pathological conditions triggering neuroinflammation. Increased [¹¹C]PK11195
8 binding potential was found in the thalamus of patients in different studies (Folkersma et al.
9 2011a; Ramlackhansingh et al. 2011; Scott et al. 2015). PET imaging with [¹¹C]DPA-713
10 revealed overall higher distribution volumes in the thalamus and brainstem of retired football
11 players, years after multiple concussions (Coughlin et al. 2015), demonstrating the applicability
12 of TSPO tracers to investigate long-term inflammatory changes.

13 Dissecting the cellular origin of the TSPO upregulation proves difficult. Initially, resident
14 microglia are activated in response to damage-associated molecular patterns, accompanied
15 by *de novo* synthesis of TSPO and therefore accounting for the majority of TSPO upregulation.
16 However, other cells also express TSPO, e.g. ED-1/CD68 positive macrophages (Lemstra et
17 al. 2007), as previously found in our model (Härtig et al. 2013), reactive astrocytes
18 (Raghavendra Rao et al. 2000; Venneti et al. 2007; Yu et al. 2010) and invading peripheral
19 macrophages. In the present study, OX-42 staining was concentrated at the contusion site,
20 showing phagocytic microglia/macrophages in the necrotic core, overlapping with the most
21 pronounced radioligand binding, similar to previous reports (Yu et al. 2010). Because BBB
22 opening after CCI is most pronounced in the first hours after injury, we believe that microglia
23 and macrophages provide the largest fraction of TSPO upregulation, as shown by [¹²³I]CLINDE
24 binding during day one and three post-injury.

25 In conclusion, our data shows that TSPO binding is markedly increased in response to TBI in
26 the contusion and brain regions not directly affected by mechanical injury. An upregulation is
27 found in the contralesional cortex and at 28 d in the ipsilateral thalamus. By employing two
28 different control groups at all investigated time points, we demonstrate that craniotomy also

1 increases [¹²³I]CLINDE binding in ipsilateral brain regions, which should be taken into account
2 when employing open-head models of TBI. [¹²³I]CLINDE might therefore be a promising
3 radioligand to visualize and quantify the neuroprotective and/or anti-inflammatory effects of
4 treatments in preclinical models of TBI.

5

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15

16 **Conflict of interest**

17 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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1 **Legend for Figures**

2

3 **Fig 1:** Focal Traumatic Brain Injury (TBI) increases *in vitro* binding of the translocator protein
4 18 kDa selective radioligand [¹²³I]CLINDE in the proximity of the contusion

5 A: Representative autoradiographs of the rat brain after sham operation (n=5), Controlled-
6 Cortical-Impact induced TBI (n=5) and craniotomy (n=3) at 6, 24, 72 hours and 28 days post
7 injury including nonspecific binding from a random animal. Slice coordinates are: Interaural
8 12.20 mm, Bregma 3.20 mm. Red/yellow areas represent high, blue/black areas represent low
9 binding of [¹²³I]CLINDE

10 B) Superimposed histological stainings (Cresyl violet and Gallays stain) of adjacent sections
11 from drug and surgery naïve rats

12 C) Image showing anatomical atlas reference (Paxinos and Watson 1998) with investigated
13 brain region (1: M1 motor cortex)

14

15 **Fig 2:** Focal Traumatic Brain Injury (TBI) increases *in vitro* binding of the translocator protein
16 18 kDa selective radioligand [¹²³I]CLINDE in remote brain regions

17 A: Representative autoradiographs of the rat brain after sham operation (n=5), Controlled-
18 Cortical-Impact induced traumatic brain injury (n=5) and craniotomy (n=3) at 6, 24, 72 hours
19 and 28 days post injury including nonspecific binding from a random animal. Slice coordinates
20 are: Interaural 5.20 mm, Bregma -3.80 mm. Red/yellow areas represent high, blue/black areas
21 represent low binding of [¹²³I]CLINDE.

22 B) Superimposed histological stainings (Cresyl violet and Gallays stain) of adjacent sections
23 from drug and surgery naïve rats

24 C) Image showing anatomical atlas reference (Paxinos and Watson 1998) with investigated
25 brain regions (1: parietal association cortex; 2: primary somatosensory cortex, barrel field; 3:
26 hippocampus; 4: thalamus with posterior thalamic nuclear group, ventral posteromedial
27 thalamic nucleus, centrolateral thalamic nucleus and oval paracentral thalamic nucleus)

28

29 **Fig 3:** Focal Traumatic Brain Injury increases binding of the translocator protein 18 kDa
30 selective radioligand [¹²³I]CLINDE *in vitro*

31 A: % binding of naïve animals in sham operation (n=5), Controlled-Cortical-Impact induced
32 traumatic brain injury (n=5) and craniotomy (n=3) at 6, 24, 72 hours and 28 days post injury.

33 A strong increase in radioligand binding is observed in the ipsilateral M1 motor cortex in
34 TBI/Craniotomy animals compared to sham at 24, 72 hours and 28 days post injury

35 [¹²³I]CLINDE binding is additionally increased in the contralateral cortex after TBI at 24 and
36 72 hours post injury.

1 Data are mean \pm SD. Significance tested with the Student's t-test. * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; **
2 $P < 0.001$

3 B: % binding of naïve animals in sham operation (n=5), Controlled-Cortical-Impact induced
4 traumatic injury (n=5) and craniotomy (n=3) at 6, 24, 72 hours and 28 days post injury
5 A strong increase in radioligand binding is observed in the cortical areas (parietal association
6 and primary somatosensory cortex, barrel field) in TBI/Craniotomy animals compared to sham
7 at 24, 72 hours and 28 days post injury. Hippocampus binding is elevated at 72 hours post
8 injury and thalamic structures show a delayed increase in binding at 28 days post injury. No
9 differences are found in the contralateral hemisphere (data not shown)

10 Data are mean \pm SD. Significance tested with the Student's t-test. * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; ***
11 $P < 0.001$

12

13 **Fig 4:** Focal Traumatic Brain Injury increases mRNA levels of the translocator protein 18 kDa
14 in the contusion

15 Increased TSPO mRNA levels in M1 motor cortex extracts of animals subjected to Controlled-
16 Cortical-Impact induced traumatic brain injury compared to sham-operated animals as
17 detected by RT-qPCR. *** $p < 0.0001$

18 Data are mean \pm SD. Significance tested with the Student's t-test

19

20 **Fig 5:** Focal Traumatic Brain Injury increases OX-42/CD11b immunopositive cells in the
21 vicinity of the contusion

22 Immunohistochemical staining for OX-42/CD11b as marker of activated
23 microglia/macrophages

24 Representative photomicrographs from one animal subjected to TBI at 72 hours post injury
25 Photomicrograph of the injured hemisphere (left) showing immunopositive cells around the
26 contusion and the corresponding autoradiograph of [123 I]CLINDE in adjacent sections
27 (middle) Processed manual overlay of both images (right) shows that most of [123 I]CLINDE
28 binding can be attributed to OX-42/CD11b immunopositive cells. Scale bar corresponds to 1
29 mm.

30

B) Nissl/Gallyas stain

low radioactivity

28 d

72 h

24 h

6 h

A) Autoradiography

Sham/control

TBI

Craniotomy

Nonspecific

high radioactivity

C) Atlas/Region of interest

A) Autoradiography

B) Nissl/Gallyas stain

C) Atlas/Region of interest

(b)

(a)

OX-42 (Cd11b)

[¹²³I]CLINDE

Overlay

